

PARTICIPANT	AGE	GENDER	EDUCATION LEVEL	STUDY FIELD	RELATION TO DIGITAL GAMES	PHASE(S)
P01	21 - 25	Male	Undergraduate Student	Games and HCI	Developer, Designer, Student and Player	I - II - III
P02	21 - 25	Male	Master's student	Hate Speech and Digital Games	Student and Player	I
P03	21 - 25	Male	Master's student	HCI	Developer, Student and Player	I
P04	36 - 40	Male	Postgraduate degree	Games and HCI	Developer, Student and Player	I
P05	36 - 40	Female	Postgraduate degree	Games, HCI and SDT	Developer, Designer, Student and Player	I
P06	21 - 25	Female	Undergraduate Student	Digital Media Systems and HCI	Student and Player	II - III
P07	26 - 30	Male	Postgraduate degree	Computer Science and HCI	Developer, Designer and Player	II - III
P08	21 - 25	Male	Undergraduate Student	Digital Media Systems and HCI	Designer, Student and Player	II - III
P09	26 - 30	Male	Undergraduate Student	Digital Media Systems, HCI and SDT	Designer and Player	II - III